

Research Article

Surface Response Methodology for Mildsteel Corrosion Inhibition by Ethyl Esters of Castor and Rubber Seed Oils

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Abstract

Surface Response Methodology was conducted for Mildsteel Corrosion Inhibition by Ethyl esters of Castor and Rubber Seed Oils. Inhibitor concentration-in-acid medium, temperature and time were considered as the independent variables, in order to know the effect of the response (dependent) variable, which is the weight loss. The design matrix was constructed on the basis of different conditions of the independent variables at varying coded levels of design consideration (-a, -1, 0, +1 and +a), upon which corrosion inhibition experiments were conducted. Contour plots were used to show the combined effects of the factors (concentration, temperature and time) on the inhibition rate of the two study samples: Castor Seed Oil (CSO) and Rubber Seed Oil, RSO. Weight loss for CSO at combined effects of temperature-concentration, time-concentration and time-temperature were found to be 33.01g, 41.11g and 43.30g respectively, while those of RSO are 30.99g 38.16g and 40.15g respectively. This indicates that the time of the corrosion reaction is the most significant factor among the three factors considered in this study, while reaction temperature is more significant, and the inhibitor concentration is least significant. This high significance of reaction time was eventually manifested at the point of optimization, which indicated the highest response value of 44.52g and 43.89g for CSO and RSO respectively. The results, therefore, identifies RSO (with least weight loss, Z=30.99g) as possessing a better inhibition efficiency, when compared to CSO, and the model equations for both samples are of second order (Pure Quadratic).

Keywords: Surface Response, Mildsteel, Corrosion Inhibition, Castor Seed Oil, Rubber Seed Oil

Received: 11 February 2017

Accepted: 26 April 2017

Introduction

Developed by G.E.P. Box and K.B. Wilson in 1951, Surface Response Methodology explores the relationships between several explanatory variables and one or more response variables. Its main idea is to use a set of designed experiments to obtain an optimal response. Box and Wilson suggested using a first-degree polynomial model to do this. Though the model was acknowledged to be only an approximation, it was recommended for usage because such a model is easy to estimate and apply, even when little is known about the process (Offurum, 2011). Once it is suspected that only significant explanatory variables are left, then a central composite design (or the like) can be employed to estimate a second-degree or higher polynomial model, even though this is still a form of approximation (Catalakaya and Sengul, 2006). Multiple response variables create difficulty, because what is optimal for one response may not be very optimal for other responses. Other extensions are used to reduce variability in a single response while targeting a specific value, or attaining a near maximum or minimum value (while preventing variability in that response from getting too large). This method of design has been widely criticized on the basis of the fact that the optimization is almost always done with a model for which the coefficients are not known (estimated). In other words, an optimum value may only look optimal, but is far from the truth because of variability in the coefficients (Box and Wilson, 1951).

In most cases, a *Contour Plot* is frequently utilized to find the response for the interaction of two variables, as well as to find the coefficients by including a large number of trials in each and combination of them. It could, also, be employed to find potentially better intermediate values between the variables, using interpolation technique (Hunter and Hunter, 2005). But as experimental runs could take a lot of time and resources, it could be difficult to point out the coefficients that are ideal (Offurum, 2011). Experimental designs used in surface response methodology usually make trade-offs between reducing variability and reducing the negative impact that can be caused by bias. In cases of comparative experiments, the preferred solution is to agree on a measurement by which competing choices can be compared, generate a sample of data from each alternative and compare the average results. Sometimes, this comparison is performed under one common set of conditions (Catalakaya and Kargi, 2007).

The present study, however, utilized contour plots to express the combined effects two variables in each case, on the response variable. The results for the two samples were also compared

Materials and Method

Design of Experiment (DOE):

To determine the effect of inhibitor concentration, temperature and time on the corrosion rate in a flow pipe, a Design of Experiments is constructed. In order to examine the combined effect of these 3 factors on the various responses and derive a model, a Central Composite Design of 2^3 (equals 8), plus six (6) centre points and six (that is 2×3) star points, leading to a total of 20 experiments for each sample were performed on the flow pipe at varying flow rates. The flow rates used were those corresponding to 20%-stroke on the flow pump (85ml/min.), 40%-stroke (150ml/min.) and 60%-stroke (210ml/min.). The factor levels, with the corresponding real values, are shown in Table 1, while the experimental design matrix is shown Table 2. The matrix for the three variables was varied at five levels ($-\alpha$, -1, 0, +1 and $+\alpha$). Accordingly, the experiments were performed in random order to avoid systematic errors, with each run replicated and the average response values used.

Different Levels of Experimental Range for effect of the Independent Variables (Inhibitor Concentration, Temperature and Time) on Corrosion Rate of the mildsteel material are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Different Levels of Experimental Range for Independent Variables

INDEPENDENT VARIABLES	SYMBOLS	CODED LEVELS				
		-1.68	-1	0	+1	+1.68
		ACTUAL LEVELS				
Inhibitor Concentration (g/L)	X_1	6.6	10	15	20	23.4
Temperature (°C)	X_2	34.8	45	60	75	85.2
Time (hour)	X_3	10.56	16	24	32	37.4

Corrosion Inhibition Assessment:

The corrosion inhibition experiments were conducted in a flow system that was designed using standard equipment. A mildsteel pipe, of mass (W_1) equals 69.2441g, was held in position on a retort stand by means clips. Using a standard dozing pump (of model: JM-15774-C07), a 10g/L concentration of the Castor Seed Oil-in-acid was fed through the pipe from a plastic reservoir (bowl). The reservoir was immersed firmly in a water bath that is set at a temperature of 45°C. The flow system was designed in such a way that the fluid is systematically recycled in a regular pattern. After 16hours of the cycle, the steel material was removed, rinsed (with distilled water), dried in an oven and weighed to

obtain a final weight, W_2 . The difference in mass, $W_1 - W_2$ was evaluated and recorded. The same procedure was adopted for other experimental runs (2 to 20) at the stipulated process parameters (dosage, temperature and time) as contained of in Table 2. The experiments were repeated using Rubber Seed Oil-in-acid, and the weight differences duly evaluated and recorded.

Contour Plot of Combined Effects of the Factors:

The contour plots of the combined effect of the factors were done using Matlab software (7.9-version). The Coefficient of Determination (R^2), as well as the Adjusted Coefficient of Determination values (adjusted R^2) for the cases involving Castor Seed Oil (CSO) and Rubber Seed Oil (RSO), were duly evaluated.

Table 2: Experimental Design Matrix for Central Composite Design for Effect of Inhibitor Concentration, Temperature and Time on Corrosion Rate in Flow Pipe.

Expt'l Runs	FACTORS					
	Coded Values			Actual Values		
	X_1	X_2	X_3	X_1	X_2	X_3
1	-	-	-	10	45	16
2	+	-	-	20	45	16
3	-	+	-	10	75	16
4	+	+	-	20	75	16
5	-	-	+	10	45	32
6	+	-	+	20	45	32
7	-	+	+	10	75	32
8	+	+	+	20	75	32
9	-1.68	0	0	6.6	60	24
10	+1.68	0	0	23.4	60	24
11	0	-1.68	0	15	34.8	24
12	0	+1.68	0	15	85.2	24
13	0	0	-1.68	15	60	10.56
14	0	0	+1.68	15	60	37.4
15	0	0	0	15	60	24
16	0	0	0	15	60	24
17	0	0	0	15	60	24
18	0	0	0	15	60	24
19	0	0	0	15	60	24
20	0	0	0	15	60	24

Results and Discussion

The results of the Experimental Design for CSO are presented in Figures 1-3, while those of their corresponding T-Statistics, P-Value and F-Statistics are presented in Table 3. Similarly, the Design of Experiments results for RSO are presented in Figures 4-6, while those of their corresponding T-Statistics, P-Value and F-Statistics are presented in Table 4. The Coefficient of Determination (R^2), as well as the Adjusted Coefficient of Determination values (adjusted R^2), are presented in Tables 5. The weight differences for both study samples, at the stipulated conditions in the design matrix, are also presented as contained in Table 6.

Fig. 1: Surface Response Plot (Castor Seed Oil) – Using Inhibitor Concentration, X (g/L) and Temperature, Y ($^{\circ}$ C) as Factors, with Weight Loss, Z (g) as Response.

Fig. 2: Surface Response Plot (Castor Seed Oil) – Using Inhibitor Concentration, X (g/L) and Time, Y (hr) as Factors, with Weight Loss, Z (g) as Response.

Fig. 3: Surface Response Plot (Castor Seed Oil) – Using Temperature, X (°C) and Time, Y (hr) as Factors, with Weight Loss, Z (g) as Response.

Table 3: Numerical Results for Model fit to Experimental Data for Castor Seed Oil, with Weight Loss as Response.

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	T Stat	Pval	F Stat
Constant	-165.9910	31.8707	-5.2083	0.0002	Sse = 4.0084e+02
X ₁	9.7468	1.7836	5.4647	0.0001	Dfe = 13
X ₂	2.9093	0.7878	3.6931	0.0027	Dfr = 6
X ₃	1.2142	1.1147	1.0891	0.2958	Ssr = 2.3916e+03
X ₁ ²	-0.3305	0.0586	-5.6390	8.0770e-05	F = 12.9271
X ₂ ²	-0.0207	0.0065	-3.1917	0.0071	Pval = 8.1036e-05
X ₃ ²	-0.0073	0.0229	-0.3207	0.7535	

$$Y = -165.9910 + 9.7468 \cdot X_1 + 2.9093 \cdot X_2 + 1.2142 \cdot X_3 - 0.3305 \cdot X_1^2 - 0.0207 \cdot X_2^2 - 0.0073 \cdot X_3^2$$

Optimization

Max.: $X_1 = 15.00\text{g/L}$, $X_2 = 70.08^\circ\text{C}$, $X_3 = 37.44\text{hrs}$, $Y(\text{fval}) = 44.52\text{g}$

Fig. 4: Surface Response Plot (RSO)- Using Inhibitor Concentration, X (g/L) and Temperature, Y ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) as Factors, with Weight Loss, Z (g) as Response.

Fig. 5: Surface Response Plot (Rubber Seed Oil) - Using Inhibitor Concentration, X (g/L) and Time, Y (hr) as Factors, with Weight Loss, Z (g) as Response.

Fig. 6: Surface Response Plot (Rubber Seed Oil) – Using Temperature, X (°C) and Time, Y (hr) as Factors, with Weight Loss, Z (g) as Response.

Table 4: Numerical Results for Model fit to Experimental Data for Rubber Seed Oil, with Weight Loss as Response

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	T Stat	Pval	F Stat
Constant	-178.4675	30.6070	-5.8309	5.8671e-05	Sse = 3.6968e+02
X ₁	9.5205	1.7129	5.5582	9.2553e-05	Dfe = 13
X ₂	3.2153	0.7565	4.2501	0.0009	Dfr = 6
X ₃	1.4676	1.0705	1.3709	0.1936	Ssr = 2.4385e+03
X ₁ ²	-0.3226	0.0563	-5.7314	6.9209e-05	F = 14.2918
X ₂ ²	-0.0232	0.0063	-3.7071	0.0026	Pval = 4.7257e-05
X ₃ ²	-0.0128	0.0220	-0.5838	0.5694	

$$Y = -178.4675 + 9.5205 \cdot X_1 + 3.2153 \cdot X_2 + 1.4676 \cdot X_3 - 0.3226 \cdot X_1^2 - 0.0232 \cdot X_2^2 - 0.0128 \cdot X_3^2$$

Optimization

Max.: X₁ = 15.00g/L, X₂ = 70.08°C, X₃ = 37.44Hrs, Y(fval) = 43.89g

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 ISSN: 2141 - 4068

Science and Education Development Inst., Nigeria

Table 5: R² and Adjusted-R² Values for DOE Data

SAMPLE	R ²	ADJUSTED-R ²
CSO-Sample A	0.8565	0.7902
RSO-Sample B	0.8684	0.8076

The results of Experimental Design (Figures 1-6) indicate that the weight loss per time (rate of corrosion) was highest in the combined effect of Time and Temperature (Figures 3 and 6), followed by that of Time and Inhibitor (Figures 2 and 5) Concentration and, finally, Temperature and Inhibitor Concentration (Figures 1 and 4) for both Samples (CSO and RSO). This is demonstrated by the respective values of the response variable, Z which is highest for 'Time-Temperature' effect (43.30g for CSO and 34.15g for RSO), but least for 'Temperature-Concentration' effect (33.01g for CSO and 30.99g for RSO). This shows that the time of the corrosion reaction is the most significant factor among the three factors considered in this study, while reaction temperature is more significant, and the inhibitor concentration is least significant. This high significance of reaction time was eventually manifested at the point of optimization, which indicated the highest response value of 44.52g and 43.89g for CSO and RSO respectively. The results, therefore, identifies RSO (with least weight loss, Z=30.99g) as possessing a better inhibition efficiency, when compared with CSO. Also, the model equations for both samples are of second order (Pure Quadratic).

Conclusion

This study reveals that mildsteel corrosion can be inhibited by ethyl esters of castor and rubber seed oils. The reaction time was found to be the most significant factor among the three factors considered in this study, while reaction temperature is more significant, and the inhibitor concentration is least significant. The design model equations (model) for both samples are of second order (Pure Quadratic). However, rubber seed oil was identified to possess a better inhibition efficiency, when compared with the castor seed oil.

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